

PUBLIC POLICIES AT THE BORDER: A LOOK AT THE BRAZIL-URUGUAY BORDER COMMITTEES

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POLICY STATEMENT

Brazil's border strip - with 15,719km of land borders - is characterized by wide political, economic, and cultural diversity, which makes it difficult to treat it in a unique way. The Brazil-Uruguay border is considered one of the most peaceful in Brazil, both for its diplomatic construction and for its identity roots, also reflected in security indicators [1]. In this territory, cooperative mechanisms have prevailed for solving cross-border problems and deepening of bilateral relations. Considering that the design of public policies in developing countries, especially those in Latin America, faces the challenge of promoting participatory models that drive sustainable development and promote social inclusion, the experience of the Border Committees is discussed. These are spaces in which proposals for the formulation of public policies are discussed binationally, with the participation of multiple actors, based on their own experiences in the territory. This experience began in the 1990s and despite the institutional challenges, it has the state's interest in its maintenance, recognizing its contributions and proposals both for the deepening of bilateral integration and for wide discussions with the Mercosur partners.

BACKGROUND

Brazil and Uruguay have bilateral relations based on “[...] historical, political and human ties between the two countries [which] allow a high degree of mutual trust [...]” [2]. Border cooperation has been a significant feature in the countries' bilateral relations, since the common border extends for 1,069 kilometers (including river, lake, land, and sea boundaries), shares natural and water resources, in addition to sheltering a significant population contingent.

In Brazil, the issue of national security coexists with the challenges related to promoting development at the borders. Paragraph 2 of article 20 of the Federal Constitution of 1988 provides that “the strip of up to one hundred and fifty kilometers wide, along the land borders, designated as the border strip, is considered fundamental for the defense of the national territory, and its occupation and use shall be regulated by law” [3]. In this sense, Law No. 6634 of May 2, 1979, establishes a series of special considerations regarding economic and commercial activities to be carried out in such territory [4]. At the same time, a Ministerial Ordinance classifies as twin cities those municipalities with more than two

thousand inhabitants “[...] cut by the border line, whether dry or river, articulated or not by infrastructure work, that present great potential of economic and cultural integration [...]” [5].

The “living borders” between Brazil and Uruguay are the scene of social dynamics that involve multiple actors, favored by the infrastructure and the geography of the border zone. In the twin cities, everyday life interactions defy political boundaries and there is significant demand for specific public policies, development projects and investments that are binationally discussed. In other municipalities covered by the border strip, for example, the sharing of water resources in hydrographic basins requires coordinated solutions and the deepening of regional integration.

Over the last few decades, the articulation between the two sides of the border has been advanced, to resolve cross-border challenges. Various institutional arrangements and legal instruments, such as the Joint Brazilian-Uruguayan Commission for the Development of the Lagoa Mirim Basin or *Cuenca de la Laguna Merín* (CLM), established in the 1960s; and the signing of the Cooperation Treaty for the Use of Natural Resources and the Development of the Lagoa Mirim Basin, dated 1977 (in force until the present day), illustrate the mutual interest in integrated development programs [6].

In 1989, the constitution of Border Committees was proposed, initially established in three pairs of cities: Chuy-Santa Vitória do Palmar and District of Chuí (which would be emancipated in 1995); Rio Branco-Jaguarão and Rivera-Santana do Livramento [7]. The Border Committees for the municipalities of Acegua-Aceguá and Quaraí-Bella Unión were established in the 1990s, with the emancipation of the Brazilian municipalities [8]. The text foresees that such Committees “[...] will promote cooperation and regional development in border areas and will provide quick and pragmatic solutions for operational problems that arise in the region”. Furthermore, Article I of its Regulation provides that “[...] the Border Committee is a Bilateral Forum for examining issues of common interest in the border region, under the jurisdiction of the Consular Posts of Brazil and Uruguay, respectively, in the border towns in which it is constituted” [7].

The Committees meetings are called alternately in the cities of both countries, under the presidency of the Brazilian or Uruguayan consular authority, who organizes the agenda. Depending on the topics to be discussed, representatives of the economic-commercial, social, and cultural agents of the respective communities will be invited to participate in the meetings, as well as agents who contribute to the discussion of scheduled topics. Delegates and Official Representatives in each Committee's area of jurisdiction will also be invited. The works of the Committees have a recommendatory character, which after being recorded in the minutes, are adopted by the consensus of their presidents, and transmitted to the Chancelleries.

Currently, such recommendations are on the agenda of the High-Level Meetings and Working Groups under the New Agenda for Border Cooperation and Development, the highest instance for border cooperation and integration between Brazil and Uruguay established in 2002 [8]. The Brazilian and Uruguayan diplomacy seeks to adopt bilateral actions that benefit the citizens of the border region,

through the active presentation of solutions, coordinating the demands raised by the Border Committees. Among some of its results, the following stand out: the Agreement for Residence, Study and Work Permits for Brazilian and Uruguayan Border Nationals; the Complementary Adjustment to the Agreement for Residence, Study and Work Permits for Brazilian and Uruguayan Border Nationals for the Provision of Health Services; the Agreement for the Creation of Binational Border Professional and/or Technical Schools and/or Institutes and for the Accreditation of Technical Courses; and the Agreement on Police Cooperation in the Investigation, Prevention and Control of Crimes.

Some of the bilaterally coordinated actions are also proposed for the Mercosur agenda and debated within the scope of Working Subgroup N°18, on Border Integration. This Group was approved by Resolution GMC No. 59/2015 and began operating in the first half of 2016 [9]. In general, the purpose of the Subgroup is to deepen the process of integration of border communities of the Member States through the application of joint programs, oriented to the integrated development of territories and communities. Among the functions of the SGT are: i) recommending the adoption of measures that may benefit the border populations of the Member States; ii) contribute, in the border zones, to greater visibility and dissemination of Mercosur and the relevant regulations for the purposes of achieving its effective implementation; and iii) promote the carrying out of specific border integration activities and the articulation of projects in different border zones with the identification of possible sources of financing. The records in the minutes of the subgroup meetings show that the demands from the Border Committees have been considered [10].

Although at certain times the recommendatory characteristic of the Border Committees has provoked its emptying, making them inefficient and with a low level of participation by national authorities [11], their relevance in the process of formulating public policies for borders has been reinforced by the Chancelleries. Recently, in June 2022, through a Joint Declaration by the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Brazil, Carlos França, and the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Uruguay, Francisco Bustillo, the space was highlighted as one of the relevant topics on their bilateral agenda [12]. Moreover, the dynamics of the Committees has become a paradigm for other Brazilian borders, as it seeks to strengthen an integrated discussion of the various aspects related to life on the border, with a view to improving the lives of its populations.

FINDINGS

Bilateral relations between Brazil and Uruguay have favored the existence of a positive relationship, allowing actors at different levels to act together in favor of solving common problems. The Border Committees have been spaces in which proposals for the formulation of public policies for different sectors are discussed binationally.

In November 2022, the five Brazil-Uruguay Border Committees met between November 7th and 11th, 2022: i) the Chuy-Chuí-Santa Vitória do Palmar Border Committee, met in Chuí-Brasil, on 07/11/2022; ii)

the Jaguarão-Rio Branco Committee met in Jaguarão-Brasil, on 11/08/2022; iii) the Aceguá-Aceguá Committee met on 11/09/2022, in the municipality of Aceguá – Brazil; iv) the Santana do Livramento-Rivera Border Committee met on 11/10/2022, in Rivera -Uruguay; v) the Border Committee Quaraí-Artigas and Barra do Quaraí-Bella Unión met on 11/11/22, in Artigas – Uruguay. In each Committee, different agenda items were discussed within thematic subcommittees.

In general, each Committee was attended by diplomatic representations from both countries, representatives of government institutions from different levels of public administration (federal, provincial and/or municipal) as well as social actors, such as educational institutions, associations and representations of groups and social movements, also from both countries. It should be noted, however, that in some meetings, some representatives did not have the presence of counterparts of the other nationality.

The agenda proposals are different for each Committee, but in general, the thematic subcommittees included the discussion of proposals on: Cooperation in Matters of Integrated Control Areas (ACI); Health Cooperation; Cooperation in Public and Judicial Security Matters; Cooperation on Labor Matters; Cooperation in Education, Vocational Training and Culture; Cooperation on Environment and Sanitation; Cooperation in Tourism and Sport; Cooperation in Trade, Transport and Other Matters; Cooperation in Local Productive Arrangements. The proposals discussed in each subcommittee are recorded in the minutes.

The absence of mechanisms for consolidation and transparency of the proposals represents a barrier in terms of monitoring their advances by society. It is known that this is an important pillar of the public policy formulation process and challenges related to transparency about the permeability of demands with decision makers, as well as monitoring the time lapse between social demands and government responses, can represent a disincentive to proactive and purposeful participation in these forums.

CONCLUSIONS

Municipalities located in border territories, although often share common everyday life and problems, are part of different states and have different treatments for similar challenges. Thus, bilateral relations between Brazil and Uruguay seek to promote border development through various initiatives. By establishing institutionalized spaces for the promotion of binational dialogue, encouraging the participation of governmental and non-governmental actors to overcome cross-border challenges, they advance in the democratic process of regional integration, seeking the joint construction of solutions to common problems, instead of isolated actions.

It is considered that the Border Committees represent privileged spaces for greater approximation and dialogue between governmental and non-governmental actors from both countries, enhancing regional integration efforts. The challenge lies in monitoring the participation and eventual advances of each

proposal, either on the bilateral agenda, or even within the scope of Working Subgroup No. 18 “Border Integration” (SGT No. 18), created in 2016, in Mercosur.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The contributions and proposals discussed by the different actors, within the Border Committees, lack the adoption of transparency mechanisms that allow wide and easy access to proposals from previous years, as well as monitoring the progress of proposals in coming years. In this regard, it is recommended:

- Create a repository of wide access with the minutes of the different Committees over the years, to map the most assiduous actors in the meetings; evaluate the inclusion/exclusion of topics from the thematic subcommittees; map thematic convergences between the different Committees; others.
- Maintain an observatory of the progress of each proposal, to monitor the status of eventual advances and implementation.
- Promote meetings of the thematic subcommittees prior to the meetings of the Committees, resuming the proposals discussed in previous meetings, evaluating their status, and presenting informed and documented proposals.
- Monitor the permeability of the Border Committees` proposals in Working Subgroup N° 18 “Border Integration” (SGT N° 18), of Mercosur, analyzing them under the prism of regional negotiations.

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